

Analytical studies on the potential of ^{238}Pu production in the large-size fast neutron power reactor

Ruslan A. Vnukov¹, Elena A. Rodina¹, Yurii S. Khomyakov¹

¹ JSC Proryv, Moscow, Russia

Corresponding author: Ruslan A. Vnukov (ravnukov@rosatom.ru)

Academic editor: Osama Ashraf ♦ **Received** 1 September 2025 ♦ **Accepted** 9 December 2025 ♦ **Published** 16 December 2025

Citation: Vnukov RA, Rodina EA, Khomyakov YS (2025) Analytical studies on the potential of ^{238}Pu production in the large-size fast neutron power reactor. Nuclear Energy and Technology 11(4): 293–299. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.11.170677>

Abstract

The possibility of obtaining ^{238}Pu in the BN-1200M (about 1,200 MWe) fast neutron power reactor is considered. To obtain products with a purity of 80–85% in terms of ^{238}Pu , options were proposed with installation of irradiation assemblies (IA) with breeding and moderating elements in the radial blanket. Neptunium and americium oxides and their mixtures were considered as target materials of the breeding elements for producing target nuclide. Zirconium hydride was considered as a moderator. The effective density of targets, IA arrangement, target/moderator materials content ratio, and irradiation time were varied. Calculations were made to determine mass and composition of produced plutonium and IA decay heat, as well as IA effect on the global and local pin-to-pin power profile in the standard fuel assemblies of the reactor core.

When using targets made of neptunium oxide, options were effective only at an effective density of approximately 1.1 g/cm³ were only effective because of self-shielding effect. Irradiation during 4–5 years ensures required 80% purity of ^{238}Pu with target purity in terms of ^{236}Pu within 2 ppm. When using Am, ^{236}Pu purity is also ensured, but ^{238}Pu fraction is somewhat lower than 80% due to the higher fraction of ^{242}Pu . The use of Am and Np mixture makes it possible to reduce the fraction of ^{236}Pu and prevent high accumulation of ^{242}Pu , but in this case ^{242}Cm accumulation should be taken into account, and appropriate time period for its decay heat reduction should be chosen.

Keywords

Radioisotope products, BN-1200 fast reactor, irradiation device, moderator element, neptunium, americium, zirconium hydride

Introduction

The demand for radioisotopes is constantly growing, this leading to a need for higher loading of existing research reactors (Gadzhiev et al. 2001; Kotchnov 2011). This is not always compatible with the main functions of such facilities (Klinov et al. 1989). If so, the cost of nuclear fuel and reactor operation should also be included in the cost of isotopes, which can significantly increase their cost.

The creation of specialized isotope production reactors is possible and is being considered, however, it is associated with rather high costs of the construction and operation of nuclear installations, which are difficult to recover by the radioisotope products.

In this regard, it is advisable to consider the possibility of producing radioisotope products in power reactors along with the main process, i.e., nuclear energy production and/or SNF reprocessing in a closed nuclear fuel cycle.

Then it can be assumed that the cost of isotopes will be relatively small and related only to the adaptation of reactor technology elements for this task.

The first attempts to organize the production of isotopes in NPP power reactors were made in the 1980–90ies in relation to RBMK reactors and BN-350 and BN-600 fast reactors (Zvonarev et al. 1994; Evdokimov et al. 1997; Mal'tsev et al. 1999), primarily in relation to the isotope ^{60}Co . Currently, industrial production of ^{60}Co is organized in RBMK reactors (Borshchev et al. 2003; Pereguda et al. 2013). However, no further construction of such reactors is envisaged, and the shutdown of all existing RBMK reactors is planned in the next 10 years. Work has been carried out on fast reactors to develop technologies for the production of ^{60}Co and a number of other isotopes, such as ^{89}Sr for medical purposes (Gadzhiev et al. 1997; Zvonarev et al. 1997) and ^{51}Cr and ^{37}Ar for scientific purposes (Zvonarev et al. 1996). Recently, the topic of producing radionuclides for energy purposes (nuclear batteries) has become relevant again (Shaginyan et al. 2022). The choice of technology depends on the level of required activity, service life and pricing policy. Isotopes ^{90}Sr and ^{238}Pu have turned the most popular.

Plutonium isotope ^{238}Pu is mainly used in radioisotope electric generators (RITEG) designed for power supply of spacecrafts and remote autonomous installations, as well as in significantly smaller numbers in cardiostimulators. ^{238}Pu has a long half-life (87.7 years) and high specific energy release (570 W/kg) in the absence of hard gamma radiation, which makes this isotope suitable for the long-term steady state power supply.

There are some limitations related to the composition of produced plutonium. Regarding the process of producing ^{238}Pu in nuclear reactors, there are two important requirements for its composition: ^{238}Pu fraction is at least 80% (Kruglov 1985) (in some publications - at least 85% (Kulikov et al. 2023)), and ^{236}Pu fraction is within 2 ppm. For medical needs, ^{236}Pu fraction should not exceed 3×10^{-7} (Gromov 1983). The undesirability of ^{236}Pu is caused by the formation of daughter decay products (^{232}U) and a source of hard γ radiation (^{208}Tl).

Production of ^{238}Pu in Russia is currently carried out mainly at Mayak Industrial Association, which is the largest Russian producer of isotopes (Ionizing Radiation Sources and Compounds 2020). The bulk of radioisotope products of Mayak are exported, accounting for up to 20% of the global isotope production. To obtain ^{238}Pu with the target parameters, a technology was developed for extracting neptunium from spent nuclear fuel and irradiating ^{237}Np in thermal neutron reactors. The potential increase in demand for ^{238}Pu , including that due to the growing number of space programs in various countries (U.S. Department of Energy 2010), has now led to the search for alternative ways of its production.

The goal of the work is to develop and calculate the feasibility of ^{238}Pu production in a fast neutron power reactor (FR) and adapt its core for this task (BN-1200M (Vasiliev

et al. 2021) was chosen as the base for this work). To achieve this goal, an analysis of potential methods of this isotope production, the configuration and arrangement of specialized irradiation devices was carried out, as well as computational analysis of the irradiation parameters and characteristics of the isotope being produced, and an assessment of the effect on the core neutronics in order to maintain them within acceptable limits.

Description of calculation models

A preliminary analysis showed that ^{237}Np irradiation in the traditional fast neutron spectrum of FR leads to the formation of ^{236}Pu as a result of the threshold reaction (n,2n) in an unacceptable amount. Therefore, in order to produce ^{238}Pu , an approach was adopted that was previously used for ^{60}Co production, i.e., creation of special irradiation devices (ID), with a moderator based on zirconium hydride, placed in the radial blanket of the BN-1200M. For computational analysis, several ID designs were developed based on a standard BN-1200M radial blanket fuel assembly containing 127 elements with 14 mm diameter, 1 mm thick cladding. Similar approaches are used, for example, in (Yusupova et al. 2022; Kashirina et al. 2025). Some of the elements, which are hereinafter referred to as moderator elements (MEL), were filled with zirconium hydride, $\text{ZrH}_{1.85}$, and the remaining elements (hereinafter referred to as breeding elements - BEL) were filled with target material, which was considered to be neptunium or americium oxides, or their mixtures of various densities. The considered designs of irradiation assemblies containing different numbers of MEL and BEL are shown in Fig. 1, and ID parameters are presented in Table 1. To reduce the impact of MEL on the fuel elements of the peripheral fuel assemblies, BEL must be placed on the periphery of the ID. Quite a number of IDs (84) were placed in the first row of the BN-1200M radial blanket, and the cross-section of the BN-1200M reactor model is shown in Fig. 2. To assess energy release nonuniformity, peripheral assemblies of the core are assumed to be heterogeneous.

Table 1. ID parameters

Parameters	Values
BEL material	NpO_2 , AmO_2 , NpO_2 - AmO_2 mixture (0.1:0.9 to 0.9:0.1 ratios)
Target effective density, g/cm^3	0.3–11.1 for NpO_2 0.3–10 for AmO_2 0.2–10 for NpO_2 - AmO_2 mixture
BEL and MEL diameter, mm	14×1
BEL target height, cm	100
Irradiation time, eff. days	Up to 3,600 (up to 11 reactor runs, 315 eff. days each)

Analytical studies were carried out to assess the possibility of meeting the requirements for commercial purity of ^{238}Pu and preventing maximum values of fuel

Figure 1. Cross-sections of ID models.

Figure 2. Cross-section of BN-1200M reactor model with 84 IDs.

element energy release from exceeding values for a standard core. Two types of disturbances of the BN-1200M neutron field caused by ID should be noted, namely: global disturbance throughout the core (a change in the distribution of the neutron flux) and local disturbance in the area of peripheral core fuel assemblies bordering ID (disturbances caused by a change in the neutron spectrum). Significant unevenness of the power profile in the fuel elements of peripheral fuel assemblies, as shown in Fig. 3, should be noted.

Max power value (~15 kW) is reached in the fuel elements located closer to the core center (farther from the disturbance source, i.e., ID with ZrH_x). This value was taken as a reference allowing exclusion of the necessity of changing core and peripheral fuel assemblies design.

Figure 3. Pin-to-pin distribution of power (kW) in peripheral fuel assemblies of the initial BN-1200M model (without ID).

Results and discussions

From the results of studies on various options of changes in the effective density, number of rows and arrangement of BELs, and irradiation time, only some of them are selected and discussed below to reflect the general specifics.

Using neptunium target

Produced plutonium mass as a general function of NpO_2 effective density is shown in Fig. 4 for ID design containing 1 row of BELs/91 MELs (irradiation time 1,440 eff. days, post-irradiation storage time 3 years).

An increase in the fuel material density leads to an increase in ^{236}Pu content. This is due to the spatial blocking effects leading to a decrease in the medium-volume density of thermal and near-thermal neutrons, and as a result, an increase in the relative fraction of fast neutrons. Based on this, a conclusion can be made that the use of effective

Figure 4. Mass of produced Pu vs NpO_2 effective density: (a) – ^{238}Pu , (b) – ^{236}Pu .

densities higher than 2 g/cm^3 is impractical from the point of view of material purity. However, it should be noted that density decrease leads to a decrease in ^{238}Pu fraction with an increase in ^{239}Pu fraction. Therefore, decrease of the effective density below 1 g/cm^3 for the irradiation time range of 1,440–2,880 eff. days is also impractical due to the high content of heavy isotopes of plutonium.

An increase of BELs number with a corresponding decrease of MELs number generally leads to a deterioration of ^{238}Pu quality in terms of ^{236}Pu isotope with an increase in the total mass of produced plutonium and ^{238}Pu fraction in it, i.e., it has the same trends as in case of density increase. Increasing BEL rows number from 1 to 2 or 3 rows leads to an increase in ^{236}Pu fraction from 3.7 ppm to 4.1 ppm and 10 ppm, and ^{238}Pu fraction - from 85% to 88% and 95%, respectively. Mass of accumulated Pu increases by 54% and 80% with an increase in the total loading of Np oxide by 83% and 233%, respectively.

In order to reduce the effects of blocking, alternative options with uniform arrangement of BELs and MELs (Alter-1 and Alter-2, respectively) were considered. In terms of BELs number, the configuration is similar to the option with two BEL rows around MEL in ID. The results of plutonium production for Alter-2 are presented in Table 2. Alter-1 option values are quite similar, however, the use of Alter-2 option leads to lower power of fuel pins in peripheral fuel assemblies and decay heat rate of ID (Table 3).

Out of the large number of options considered, four most suitable options have been identified, in which ^{238}Pu isotopic composition quality parameters can be achieved

with 1.1 g/cm^3 accepted density of the target material with NpO_2 . Generalized estimates of production parameters to ensure ^{238}Pu fraction equal to at least 85% and 80% are given in Tables 3, 4, respectively. Based on the integral assessment of accumulation in the ID, extrapolations were made to determine the annual reactor capacity when the 1st row of the radial blanket is fully filled with 84 IDs. An estimate has also been made of the required average annual number of simultaneously irradiated IDs to achieve a traditional capacity of about 3 kg/year.

The results show the potential of producing ^{238}Pu in a 1,200 MWe reactor in large amount exceeding the existing estimates of its world current consumption. Despite the local power peak, the fuel element power in the peripheral fuel assemblies of the proposed configurations does not exceed the maximum values for the initial core design with the standard radial blanket. The linear power on the fuel element in the core as a whole does not exceed 500 W/cm in all selected options. ID installation leads to a decrease in the reactivity by $-0.6\% \Delta k/k$, and as the assemblies are irradiated, the effect decreases to -0.4% . The loss of reactivity can be eliminated by changing the fuel plutonium enrichment in the standard fuel assemblies.

Using americium target

Americium, as well as neptunium, is a minor actinide, the incineration of which. On the one hand, it is a vital task of fast reactors. On the other hand, it is a potential source of ^{238}Pu , which is the main nuclide related to the transmutation

Table 2. Results of plutonium production for Alter-2 ID with NpO₂ target with 1.1 g/cm³ eff. density

Irradiation time, eff. days	Fraction, ppm		Plutonium isotope composition, %				Pu mass, kg/year
	²³⁶ Pu	²³⁸ Pu	²³⁹ Pu	²⁴⁰ Pu	²⁴¹ Pu	²⁴² Pu	
360	4.3 / 3.9	94.8	4.7	0.3	0.1	0.0	66
720	3.6 / 3.4	91.2	7.5	0.9	0.5	0.0	62
1,080	3.0 / 3.1	88.4	9.1	1.4	0.9	0.1	58
1,440	2.7 / 2.8	86.1	10.3	2.0	1.4	0.2	53
1,800	2.7 / 2.6	84.2	11.2	2.5	1.8	0.4	49
2,160	2.3 / 2.4	82.4	11.8	3.0	2.2	0.6	45
2,520	2.0 / 2.0	80.8	12.3	3.6	2.6	0.8	41
2,880	1.9 / 2.0	79.2	12.7	4.1	3.0	1.0	37

Table 3. Parameters of plutonium production with limited ²³⁸Pu fraction (85%)

Characteristics \ ID options	1 BEL row	2 BEL rows	Alter-1	Alter-2
Irradiation time, eff. days.	1,440	1,800	1,800	1,440
Storage time, years	3	3	2	2
²³⁶ Pu fraction, ppm	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.7
²³⁸ Pu fraction, %	85	86	85	86
Production rate in the reactor, kg/year	27	39	52	53
Average annual ID number for production rate about 3 kg/year	9.3	6.7	4.9	4.7
Max power of fuel element in the peripheral fuel assembly, kW	15.7	11.4	14.3	11.8
Max linear power of fuel element, W/cm	484	488	480	490
ID decay heat, kW	1.42	2.15	3.12	2.98
Reactivity loss at the beginning of the core lifetime, Δk/k %	-0.5%	-0.5%	-0.6%	-0.6%

Table 4. Parameters of plutonium production with limited ²³⁸Pu fraction (80%)

Characteristics \ ID options	1 BEL row	2 BEL rows	Alter-1	Alter-2
Irradiation time, eff. days.	2,160	2,880	2,880	2,520
Storage time, years	3	3	0	0
²³⁶ Pu fraction, ppm	1.3	1.7	1.9	2.0
²³⁸ Pu fraction, %	81	82	81	81
Production rate in the reactor, kg/year	23	32	39	41
Average annual ID number for production rate about 3 kg/year	11.2	7.9	6.4	6.2

of ²⁴¹Am. The key features of producing ²³⁸Pu from ²⁴¹Am are the absence of a direct channel for ²³⁶Pu formation, this, of course, being an obvious advantage, and a more significant accumulation of ²⁴²Pu (at least 17%) to dilute the target isotope. Calculations show that maximum ²³⁸Pu fraction is about 76%, although ²³⁶Pu fraction does not exceed 1 ppm. This is due to decay pattern of ²⁴²Am, which is a daughter product of the radiation capture reaction by ²⁴¹Am. According to it, ²⁴²Cm is produced with a probability of 82.7%, decaying with a half-life of 162.8 days to ²³⁸Pu and with a probability of 17.3% - to ²⁴²Pu.

In this case, ²³⁸Pu can also be produced in a fast neutron spectrum, but due to the relatively low neutron flux in the radial blanket area the moderator increases the effectiveness of the process, i.e., the specific production rate per target mass unit as shown in Table 5. However, the moderator decreases ²³⁸Pu fraction to 64–65% by accelerating its transmutation to ²³⁹Pu.

Another feature of this ²³⁸Pu production method is the increased ID decay heat caused by ²⁴²Cm. It can reach 3.5–20 kW after 2 years of storage, depending on the mass of the loaded americium. This may require longer ID storage time after irradiation.

Using target made of NpO₂ and AmO₂ mixture

The combined use of americium and neptunium oxides was studied to obtain a synergistic effect from the

advantages of individual components, namely: required high ²³⁸Pu content, typical for Np, and low ²³⁶Pu content inherent in Am target.

In fast neutron spectrum, in the absence of a moderator, it is possible to obtain ²³⁸Pu purity up to 79% with a 1.9 ppm ²³⁶Pu fraction and 18% ²⁴²Pu fraction with a ratio of Np/Am = 1/9 and irradiation time of 2,880 eff. days. As regards two-band ID model with BELs located on the periphery and MELs located in the center, it is possible to ensure the required purity in terms of ²³⁶Pu and about 80% ²³⁸Pu fraction with low densities (0.2 g/cm³). In this case, it is necessary to increase neptunium fraction in order to maintain ²³⁸Pu fraction equal to 80%. It is recommended to adopt Np/Am = 1.0/1.1 ratio typical for VVER SNF after its limited storage during of 7–8 years. The results of calculations of various ID options with ZrH_x are given in Table 6.

As regards the unlocked ID options (Alter-1 and Alter-2), the required ²³⁸Pu quality can be reached with a fuel material density of 1 g/cm³. The two options are similar in terms of parameters and, in terms of produced plutonium mass, are ahead of the symmetrical ID options discussed above. The dynamics of changes in the operating time of ²³⁸Pu is shown in Table 7.

For given power density of the fuel element, power values of the core fuel assemblies are close to those for ID option with Np density of 1.11 g/cm³ and do not exceed 15 kW.

Table 5. Parameters of production for max ^{238}Pu fraction with AmO_2 target

Characteristics \ ID options	2 BEL rows	3 BEL rows	5 BEL rows	No MEL
Effective density, g/cm^3	0.7	0.7/7	0.7/7	7
Irradiation time, eff. days	990/2,880	990/1,440	1,080/1,800	1,800/2,880
^{236}Pu fraction, ppm	0.0/0.0	0.0/0.3	0.1/0.5	0.8/1.1
^{238}Pu fraction, %	73/64	74/77	75/77	77/76
Pu fraction, %	22/47	18/5.4	11/6.0	6.0/9.9
Production rate in reactor, kg/year	31/26	34/71	26/83	85/102
Average annual ID number for production of about 3 kg/year	8.1/9.7	7.4/3.5	9.7/3.0	3.0/2.5

*storage time is not indicated, since none of the options meets purity requirements in terms of ^{238}Pu .

Table 6. Parameters of ^{238}Pu production in case of combined use of Am and Np

Characteristics \ ID options	1 BEL row	2 BEL rows	Alter-1	Alter-2
Irradiation time, eff. days	2,160	2,880	2,880	2,520
Storage time, years	3	3	0	0
^{236}Pu fraction, ppm	1.3	1.7	1.9	2.0
^{238}Pu fraction, %	81	82	81	81
Production rate in the reactor, kg/year	23	32	39	41
Average annual ID number for production of about 3 kg/year	11.2	7.9	6.4	6.2
Characteristics \ ID options	1 BEL row	2 BEL rows	4 BEL rows	
Irradiation time, eff. days		360	360	1,080
^{236}Pu fraction, ppm		1	2	1.7
^{238}Pu fraction, %		78	81	80
Pu fraction, %		18	17	32
Production rate in the reactor, kg/year		19	37	38
Average annual ID number for production of about 3 kg/year		13.3	6.8	6.6

*ID storage time for presented options is 0 years

Table 7. Results of plutonium production for Alter-1 and Alter-2 ID

Irradiation time, eff. days	Fraction, ppm		Plutonium isotope composition, %				Pu mass, kg/year
	^{236}Pu	^{238}Pu	^{239}Pu	^{240}Pu	^{241}Pu	^{242}Pu	
360	2.8	84.2	2.7	0.3	0.1	12.8	51.5
720	2.5	83.7	5.0	0.6	0.3	10.5	55.5
1,080	1.9	82.1	7.1	0.9	0.6	9.3	55.2
1,440	1.8	80.4	8.7	1.4	1.1	8.5	52.2
1,800	1.6	78.7	10.0	1.9	1.6	7.9	48.4
2,520	1.1	75.2	11.7	3.4	2.6	7.0	45.6
2,880	1.0	73.5	12.2	4.3	3.2	6.8	39.0

After irradiation for 1,440–1,485 effective days and post-irradiation storage for 30 days ID decay heat ranges from 50.9 to 52.1 kW. Thus, when using Am in IDs, it is necessary to store them, as the standard core fuel assemblies, in the in-vessel storage or boron shielding rod cells to reduce ID decay heat level.

Conclusion

Analysis of the possibility of combining the solution of two problems, namely: transmutation of long-lived MA (Np, Am) and production of heat-generating radioisotope, ^{238}Pu , has shown that, in accordance with the requirements for its purity, this is potentially possible with a heterogeneous transmutation pattern using moderator in the radial blanket. Production parameters and isotopic composition of produced plutonium depend significantly on the design of irradiation device, i.e., moderator/target material volume ratio (MEL and BEL numbers), density of the target material, patterns of BEL and MEL arrangement in the ID and irradiation time.

After analyzing and optimizing a large number of options, four ID designs with NpO_2 are proposed ensuring

^{238}Pu production time in accordance with the requirements for ^{238}Pu content (at least 85%) and ^{236}Pu content (within 2 ppm) with a total production rate of ~25 to ~50 kg/year for full loading of the first row of the BN-1200M radial blanket. Np density in the target should not exceed 1.1 g/cm^3 . To decrease ^{236}Pu fraction to the value not exceeding 2 ppm, it is necessary to store ID with 85% purity in terms of ^{238}Pu for 2–3 years before reprocessing, and there is no need for storing in case of 80% purity.

These potential production volumes may and most likely actually exceed the world demand for this isotope; to achieve realistic requirements of 3 kg/year, ^{238}Pu will require installation of 5 to 10 ID in the radial blanket of the BN-1200M. ID presence may cause an increase in power of the core peripheral fuel assemblies adjacent to ID. However, in spite of the disturbance of the power profile at the core boundary in the proposed options, the fuel element power does not exceed the maximum values of 15 kW for standard fuel elements, and the linear power of the hottest fuel pins of the core is within 500 W/cm.

Calculations of decay heat values for proposed ID options after storage during 30 days gave a value of about 3 kW, this making possible their unloading taking into

account similar values for standard fuel assemblies or those with homogeneous use of MA.

It has been demonstrated that in case of using AmO₂ as a target material, the resulting ²³⁸Pu contains no more than 1 ppm of ²³⁶Pu. However, ²³⁸Pu isotope fraction does not reach 80%. When irradiating NpO₂ - AmO₂ mixture, it is possible to obtain ²³⁸Pu fraction above 80% and low

content of ²³⁶Pu (about 1–2 ppm), but it requires ID storage after irradiation, as in the case of standard fuel assemblies.

ID designs with unlocked Alter type working elements show the best performance in terms of ²³⁸Pu production per unit mass of heavy metal. However, in general, ID design can be optimized by clarifying the requirements for the target product.

References

- Borshchev VP, Zhukov IV, Mel'nikov OP, Rozhdestvenskii MI, Cherkashov YuM, Burlakov EV, Kvator VM, Gorbunov EK, Lebedev VI, Fursov AN, Shevchenko VG, Kuznetsov VYu, Mironov YuI, Romanenko VI, Ryakhovskikh VI (2003) Possibilities for Producing Radionuclides in Nuclear Power Plants with RBMK Reactors. *Atomic Energy* 95(6) 856–861. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:aten.0000018999.03459.79>
- Evdokimov VP, Vasiliev BA, Zvonaryov AV, Zinoviev AI, Kravchenko IN, Matveev VI, Matveenko IP, Poplavsky VM, Rodionov NG, Smetanin EYa, Khomyakov YuS, Cherny VA (1997) Method of Production of Radioactive Isotopes in Fast Neutron Reactor and Fast Neutron Nuclear Reactor. Patent No.2076362. <https://patents.google.com/patent/RU2076362C1/ru>
- Gadzhiev GI, Zvonarev AV, Korolkov AS, Kravchenko IN, Matveenko IP, Pavlovich VB, Poplavsky VM, Smetanin EYa, Khomyakov YuS, Cherny VA (1997) Method of Obtaining Compound Based on Strontium-89. Patent No.2080878. <https://patentdb.ru/patent/2080878>
- Gadzhiev GI, Efimov VN, Zhemkov IYu, Korol'kov AS, Polyakov VI, Shtynda YuE, Revyakin Yu L (2001) Some Experimental Studies Performed at BOR-60. *Atomic Energy* 91(5) Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 913–922. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1014265807449>
- Gromov BV, Savel'eva VI, Shevchenko VB (1983) *Chemical Technology of Irradiated Fuel* [in Russian]. Moscow, Energoatomizdat, 88 pp.
- *Ionizing Radiation Sources and Compounds* (2020) Digital Assets, 60 pp. <https://www.po-mayak.ru/upload/iblock/5ed/rppuri0rx7gz73msmt7umwdsp1xxde70.pdf>
- Kashirina VE, Nevinitisa VA, Kotov YaA, Fomichenko PA, Kolesov VV (2025) Investigation of the effectiveness of heterogeneous burning of minor actinides in a fast reactor reflector. *Problems of atomic science and technology. Series: Nuclear and Reactor Constants* 1: 44–55. <https://vant.ippe.ru/en/year2025/1/neutron-constants/2644-4.html>
- Klinov AV, Mamelin AV, Toporov YuG (1989) Research reactors for radionuclide production at the scientific-research institute for atomic reactors (Niiar). *Soviet Atomic Energy* 67: 656–661. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01123205>
- Kotchnov OYu (2011) *Scientific and Technological Development of Production of ⁹⁹Mo Radionuclide for Medical Purposes and Molybdenum-Techneium Generators Using VVR-C Research Reactor*, extended abstract of dissertation by Doctor of Technology, Moscow 54. <https://www.dissercat.com/content/nauchno-tekhnologicheskoe-razvitiye-proizvodstva-radionuklida-meditsinskogo-naznacheniya-99mo>
- Kruglov AK (1985) *Radionuclides Production in Reactors* [In Russian]. Moscow, Energoatomizdat, 256 pp.
- Kulikov GG, Shmelyov AN, Glebov VB, Apse VA, Kulikov EG (2023) Neutron Physics Foundations of the Large-Scale Development of ²³⁸Pu for Autonomous Energy Sources *Izvestiya vuzov. Yadernaya Energetika* 2: 162–168. <https://doi.org/10.26583/npe.2023.2.13>
- Mal'tsev VV, Karpenko AI, Chernov IA, Golovin VV (1999) Experience with ⁶⁰Co production in BN-600. *Atomic Energy* 86(3): 219–221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02672950>
- Pereguda VI, Shmakov LV, Gubin SI, Gorbunov EK, Kondratyev AA, Fursov AN (2013) Method of Production of Cobalt-60 in the Channel Type Nuclear Reactor. Patent of Invention RU 2473992 C1. 27.01.2013. Application No. 2011141390/07 of 12.10.2011. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=37505990>
- Shaginyan RA, Korobeynikov VV, Stogov VYu (2022) Studies on Effectiveness of Various Isotopes Production as a Function of Energy Structure and Density of Neutron Flux. Preprint FEI–3302, Obninsk, SSC RF IPPE, 40 pp.
- U.S. Department of Energy. Startup Plan for Plutonium-238 Production for Radioisotope Power Systems [Digital Assets] (2010) Report to Congress. June 2010 / U.S. Department of Energy. https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2015/09/f26/Final_Startup_Plan_for_Plutonium238.pdf
- Vasiliev BA, Belov SB, Kiselev AV, Eliseev VA, Khomiakov YuS, Rodina EA (2021) Unification of the BN-1200 reactor core designs with MOX and MNUP fuel. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 382: 111387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2021.111387>
- Yusupova AE, Yusupov AN, Zhemkov IYu, Naboyshchikov YuV (2022) Radiation Characteristics of Non-Irradiated MA Elements and Assemblies for Minor Actinides Utilization [Digital Assets] / A. E. Yusupova, et al, Annual Scientific Report of JSC SSC NI-IAR, Dimitrovgrad, 191–192. https://www.elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_49749389_65918710.pdf
- Zvonarev AV, Korobeynikov VV, Matveyenko IP, Suslov IR, Khomyakov YuS, Tsibulya AM, Tchyornii VI, Shkol'nik VS, Netsvet VP, Skorikov NV, Zinov'ev AI, Rodionov NG (1994) ⁶⁰Co production in BN-350 reactors. *Atomic Energy* 77(6): 940–943. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02415548>
- Zvonarev AV, Khomyakov YuS, Evdokimov VP, Kochetkov AL, Tsibulya AM, Chernyi, VA, Gavrin VN, Abdurashitov DN, Vereitenkin EP, Kornoukhov VN (1996) Possibilities of obtaining intense (anti)neutrino sources in fast power reactors. *Atomic Energy* 80(2): 105–110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02414632>
- Zvonarev AV, Matveenko IP, Pavlovich VB, Podsoblyayev DA, Poplavskii VM, Smetanin EYa, Khomyakov YuS, Tsibulya AM, Chernyi VA, Gadzhiev GI, Korol'kov AS, Kravchenko IN (1997) ⁸⁹Sr production in fast reactors. *Atomic Energy* 82(5): 394–397. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02418738>